

Report from experiment 2025

GAČR 25-16403S

NEW WASTE MATERIAL

1. Envisan recycled material, 09/24, „concrete+aerated concrete“
2. Envisan recycled material, 09/24, „mortar from masonry“
3. Envisan recycled material, 09/24, „mixture including bricks and concrete“
4. Envisan recycled material, 09/24, „brick masonry“

First testing of materials (3.2.2025):

1. **Envisan recycled material, 09/24, „concrete+aerated concrete“**
 - Rapid sedimentation
 - pH = 9,0
 - Does not flow through the filter, "filters better," but settles quickly when transferring from falcon tubes to vials

2. Envisan recycled material, 09/24, „mortar from masonry“

- Rapid sedimentation
- Sand absorbs more water, "heavier"
- pH = 8.0
- Slower filtration

3. Envisan recycled material, 09/24, „mixture including bricks and concrete“

- Rapid sedimentation
- pH = 8,0
- Very similar material to 2)

- Fastest filtration (water flows through the grains and is filtered with the highest speed)

4. Envisan recycled material, 09/24, „brick masonry“

- Rapid sedimentation
- pH = 7,5-8,0
- Slowest filtration of all – most "clogged"

QUESTIONS

- The whitest (1) – contains the most gypsum?
- Materials (2) and (3) are similar
- The total volume is approx. 10 ml, but 10 g of WCF has a volume of 15 ml – lower composites, or increase the amount?
 - o 15 ml (1) = 15 g (1) (by volume) = 10 g WCF (by volume)
- Mix with WCF? E.g. 10 g (1-4) and 5 g WCF
- Behaviour quite similar to sand – **rapid sedimentation**
- Larger particles and very **loose** material – poorer grain cohesion?

a) What volume/weight?

b) Sedimentation

c) Problem with no filtering – already with the first 20 ml

Testing other possibilities (4.2.2025)

a) All four materials (by volume) 0.25:0.25:0.25:0.25

Material 1 = 4 ml = 4.1 g

Material 2 = 4 ml = 4.3 g

Material 3 = 4 ml = 4.9 g

Material 4 = 4 ml = 4.3 g

b) Material 3 (mixture including bricks and concrete) and 4 (mortar masonry) with WCF column (by volume) 5ml:5ml:5ml

Material 3 = 5 ml = 5.6 g

Material 4 = 5 ml = 5.1 g

WCF column = 5 ml = 3.1 g

c) All four materials (by volume) with WCF column 3ml:3ml:3ml:3ml:3ml

Material 1 = 3 ml

Material 2 = 3 ml

Material 3 = 3 ml

Material 4 = 3 ml

WCF column = 3 ml

All types of samples (a-c) – sedimentation of materials (largest particles at the bottom, smallest at the top)

After 30-60 seconds of vibration:

FEASIBILITY TESTING 13.2.

- Optimal weight of WCF/HM/gypsum and volume of suspension/saline
- Only two materials:
 - 1 – Envisan recycled material, 09/24, „concrete+aerated concrete“ **HM1**
 - 2 – Envisan recycled material, 09/24, „mortar from masonry“ **HM2**
- Testing of gypsum addition
- Testing of two temperatures: 20 °C a 30 °C
- All in tetraplicates
- Variant without addition of biocementation solution (4x WCF, 4x WCF with gypsum)

Type of sample	WCF (g)	HM1 (g)	HM2 (g)	gypsum	suspension	saline	Adjustment of pH (2M HCl)
Variant 1	24	-	-	2.4	10	4	2
Control of variant 1	24	-	-	2.4	-	14	2
Variant 2	26.4	-	-	-	10	4	2
Control of variant 2	26.4	-	-	-	-	14	2
Variant 3	-	24	-	2.4	10	-	-
Control of variant 3	-	24	-	2.4	-	10	-
Variant 4	-	26.4	-	-	10	-	-
Control of variant 4	-	26.4	-	-	-	10	-
Variant 5	-	-	24	2.4	10	-	-
Control of variant 5	-	-	24	2.4	-	10	-
Variant 6	-	-	26.4	-	10	-	-
Control of variant 6	-	-	26.4	-	-	10	-

EXPERIMENT No. 12

- **3.3.:** inoculation of Erlenmeyer flasks (3x400 ml) with LB + sodium sesquicarbonate (100 ml/l) at 9:00 → cultivation for 48 hours, 20 °C, 150 rpm
 - pH of medium = 10,0

- **4.3.:** inoculation of Erlenmeyer flasks (3x400 ml) with LB + sodium sesquicarbonate (100 ml/l) at 7:30 → cultivation for 24 hours, 30 °C, 150 rpm

- **5.3.:** all Erlenmeyer flasks removed at 9:00
 - OD₆₀₀ (20 °C) = 1,23
 - OD₆₀₀ (30 °C) = 1,03
 - Bacterial suspension transferred to large centrifuge cuvettes (6x 30 °C, 3x 20 °C) → centrifugation for 10 minutes, 10 000 g, 4 °C
 - Supernatant was removed → 70 ml (30 °C) or 80 ml (20 °C) of saline was added into each cuvette
 - 30 °C: 520 ml of suspension with OD₆₀₀ = 5,15
 - 20 °C: 240 ml of suspension with OD₆₀₀ = 4,8
 - Sample preparation: pre-weighed amount of WCF/HM/gypsum transferred into to the prepared vials and thoroughly mixed → addition of suspension/saline/HCl → mixture stirred with a sterile spatula/spoon and pores mechanically squeezed out → vibration of 30-60 seconds (depending on visual need to remove pores)
 - Cultivation of samples and negative controls at 30 °C and selected samples at 20 °C (due to a lack of shakers, cultivation was performed on a table in the laboratory at 20-21 °C)

- **7.3.:** addition of MICP (biocementation) solution and saline (14:00)
 - **5 ml of MICP solution/saline** (the plan is to add every 48-72 hours)
 - Findings after 48 hours of cultivation:
 - Differences in samples on the laboratory table (20 °C) and at 30 °C – samples cultivated at 30 °C were significantly drier, „the mud“ was gone, it was dry and slightly cracked on the surface, unlike the samples at 20 °C
 - **Samples 20 (WCF):** no flow through
 - **Samples 21 (HM1) and samples 22 (HM2):** slowly dripping (perhaps only through one hole)
 - **Samples 23 (WCF) with gypsum:** no flow through
 - **Samples 24 (HM1) and samples 25 (HM2) with gypsum:** the slowest dripping of all variants (higher temperature, addition of gypsum)
 - **Samples 26 (WCF+20 °C):** no flow through
 - **Samples 27 (HM1+20 °C) and samples 28 (HM2+20 °C):** flow through started after a while, but very slowly – slow dripping
 - **Samples 29 (WCF+20 °C) with gypsum:** no flow through
 - **Samples 30 (HM1) and samples 31 (HM2+20 °C) with gypsum:** flow through started after a while, but more slowly than with the previous set of samples (27-28)
 - Differences in samples **32, 33** (without addition of MICP solution) – some completely dry, other still damp „mud“
 - **Controls of WCF** – sample 20-6 flows through, other no
 - **Controls of HM1 and HM2** – flow through faster than samples – different behaviour of particles when suspension/saline is added

Sample 26-1: WCF, 20 °C (hard to see, but the „mud“ is still wet)

Sample 27-1: HM1, 20 °C (not so dry)

Sample 28-1: HM2, 20 °C (not so dry)

Really slow dripping with HM1 and HM2, slowest with WCF

Sample 29-1: WCF+gypsum, 20 °C (again not so dry)

Sample 30-1: HM1+gypsum, 20 °C (again not so dry) – less losses of material than with WCF

Sample 31-1: HM2+gypsum, 20 °C (not so dry) – less losses of material than with WCF

Sample 32-1: HM2+gypsum, 20 °C (not so dry) – less losses of material than with WCF

Sample 20-1: WCF, 30 °C – dry surface of sample, high material losses during preparation

Sample 21-1: HM1, 30 °C dry surface of sample

Sample 22-1: HM2, 30 °C – dry surface of sample

Sample 23-1: WCF+gypsum, 30 °C – dry surface of sample

Sample 24-1: HM1+gypsum, 30 °C – dry surface of sample

Sample 25-1: HM2+gypsum, 30 °C – dry surface of sample

Sample 32-1: WCF, 30 °C, cracks on the surface of sample

- **10.3.:** addition of 5 ml MICP/saline
 - All samples flow through – pH of filtrates will be measured on Wednesday (12th March)
 - Samples at 20 °C – significantly wetter than samples at 30 °C, slower flow through
 - WCF+gypsum (sample 29-4) did not flow through at all
 - Samples at 30 °C – significantly drier than samples at 20 °C, faster flow through
 - Control of WCF (sample 20-5) did not flow through at all

- **12.3.:** addition of 5 ml MICP/saline
 - Samples 20: flow through (except the sample 20-2), filtrate evaporated
 - Samples 21: flow through, mold on the surface, filtrate evaporated
 - Samples 22: flow through, mold on the surface, filtrate evaporated (except the sample 22-4)
 - Samples 23: not flow through (1-2 ml), filtrate evaporated
 - Samples 24: flow through, mold on the surface, smell, filtrate evaporated
 - Samples 25: flow through, mold on the surface
 - Samples 26: flow through, slow dripping
 - Samples 27: flow through
 - Samples 28: flow through, mold on the surface
 - Samples 29: flow through (1 ml – except the sample 29-3)

- Samples 30: flow through (except the sample 30-3)
- Samples 31: 31-1 and 31-2 not flow through, 31-3 and 31-4 flow through with mold on the surface
- Samples 32,33: wet surface, starts to crack
- Controls 20: flow through (except the samples 20-5), pH = 7.5-8.0
- Controls 21: flow through, filtrate evaporated
- Controls 22: flow through, pH = 7.5
- Controls 23: flow through (except the sample 23-7), filtrate evaporated
- Controls 24: flow through, filtrate evaporated
- Controls 25: flow through, filtrate evaporated

	12.3. (pH)	status
20-1	-	Flow through
20-2	-	Not flow through
21-1	-	Flow through, mold on the surface
21-2	-	Flow through, mold on the surface
22-2	8.5	Flow through, mold on the surface
22-3	7.5	Flow through, mold on the surface
23-3	8.5	Not flow through
23-4	9.5	Not flow through
24-2	8.0	Flow through, mold on the surface
24-3	7.9	Flow through, mold on the surface
25-1	8.5	Flow through, mold on the surface
25-2	7.5	Flow through, mold on the surface
26-1	8.0	Flow through
26-2	7.5	Flow through
27-1	8.0	Flow through
27-2	7.5	Flow through
28-1	8.0	Flow through, mold on the surface
28-2	7.9	Flow through, mold on the surface
29-1	8.5	Not flow through
29-2	7.5	Not flow through
30-1	8.0	Flow through
30-3	7.9	Flow through
31-1	8.0	Not flow through
31-2	7.5	Not flow through

- **14.3.:** addition of 5 ml MICP/saline
 - o Samples 22 a 25 – mold inside the samples
- **17.3.:** addition of 5 ml MICP/saline
- **20.3.:** addition of 5 ml MICP/saline
- **21.3.:** addition of 5 ml MICP/saline
- **25.3.:** addition of 5 ml MICP/saline
 - o Contamination of samples no. 27 (1-4), 30 (1-4), 31-2

Samples without added MICP solution – slowly drying, with slight surface cracking

32-1 (without MICP addition) - WCF

33-1 (without MICP addition) – WCF with gypsum

20-1 WCF (30 °C) – not flow through

23-1 WCF+gypsum (30 °C) – not flow through

21-1 HM1 (30 °C) – mold on the surface, smell

24-1 HM1+gypsum (30 °C) – mold on the surface, smell

22-1 HM2 (30 °C) – mold on the surface

25-1 HM2+gypsum (30 °C)

26-1 WCF (20 °C) – not flow through, filtrate

29-1 WCF+gypsum (20 °C) – not flow through, filtrate

27-1 HM1 (20 °C)

30-1 HM1+gypsum (20 °C) – not flow through

28-1 HM2 (20 °C) – not flow through

31-1 HM2+gypsum (20 °C)

STERILE SAMPLES (CONTROLS)

20-5 WCF (30 °C)

22-6 HM2 (30 °C)

23-5 WCF+gypsum (30 °C)

25-5 HM2+gypsum (30 °C)

- Conclusion: filtrate evaporated in samples at 30 °C (28 °C and 20 °C – filtrate not evaporated)

- **28.3.:** addition of 5 ml MICP/saline

- **31.3.:** addition of 5 ml MICP/saline

- **3.4.:** taking photo of sample + addition of 5 ml MICP/saline

Samples without added MICP solution – slowly drying, with slight surface cracking

20-1 WCF (30 °C)

23-1 WCF+gypsum (30 °C)

21-1 HM1 (30 °C) – mold on the surface, smell

24-1 HM1+gypsum (30 °C) – mold on the surface, smell

22-1 HM2 (30 °C) – mold on the surface

25-1 HM2+gypsum (30 °C)

26-1 WCF (20 °C) – not flow through, filtrate

29-1 WCF+gypsum (20 °C) – not flow through, filtrate

27-1 HM1 (20 °C) – not flow through

30-1 HM1+gypsum (20 °C) - not flow through

28-1 HM2 (20 °C) - not flow through

31-1 HM2+gypsum (20 °C) – mold

32-1 (without addition of MICP)

33-1 (without addition of MICP) – WCF with gypsum

STERILE SAMPLES (CONTROLS)

20-5 WCF (30 °C)

23-5 WCF+gypsum (30 °C) – not flow through

21-5 HM1 (30 °C)

24-5 HM1+gypsum (30 °C)

22-5 HM2 (30 °C)

25-5 HM2+gypsum (30 °C)

- **4.4.:** remove the solution which was not filter (on
 - o Remove the lids from all samples
 - o Dry at 20 °C (open on the table in laboratory) and at 30 °C (shakers at 30 °C, 30 rpm)

- **5.5.:** samples drying finished

20-1 WCF (30 °C)

23-1 WCF+gypsum (30 °C)

21-1 HM1 (30 °C) – mold on the surface

24-1 HM1+gypsum (30 °C) – mold on the surface, smell

Samples 22-1 – pores in the sample

22-1 HM2 (30 °C) – mold on the surface

25-1 HM2+gypsum (30 °C) – mold on the surface

26-1 WCF (20 °C) – not flow through, filtrate

29-1 WCF+gypsum (20 °C) – not flow through, filtrate

27-1 WCF (20 °C) – not flow through, filtrate

30-1 WCF (20 °C) – not flow through, filtrate

28-1 HM2 (20 °C) – not flow through

31-1 HM2+gypsum (20 °C) – mold

32-1 (without addition of MICP) - WCF

33-1 (without addition of MICP) – WCF with gypsum

32, 33 - Samples perfectly dry, no cracks

28-1 – cracks in discontinuous material (before any handling of the sample)

STERILE SAMPLES (CONTROLS)

20-5 WCF (30 °C)

23-5 WCF+gypsum (30 °C) – rough surface

21-5 HM1 (30 °C)
- non-uniform surface

24-5 HM1+gypsum (30 °C)

22-5 HM2 (30 °C)

25-5 HM2+gypsum (30 °C)

- Samples 21 (1-4): pores inside – non-removal of pores by vibration
 - Sample 22-2: mold on the surface of the sample
 - Sample 24-1: separation of layers on the surface
 - Sample 31-3: mold on the surface of the sample
 - Samples 28 (1-2): mold on the bottom of the sample
 - Samples 28 (2-3): cracks/pores in these samples
 - Sample 27-1: cracks
 - Sample 23-5: WCF control – sample cracking
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- **6.5.:** samples were handed over to the CTU

13.5. Meeting – VŠCHT + ČVUT

- different technology of preparation samples - YES
- using of gypsum - YES
- vibrations for remove the pores - YES
- Find out how much material HM2 we have?

EXPERIMENT No. 13

- **26.5.:** inoculation of Erlenmeyer flasks (5x400 ml) with LB + sodium sesquicarbonate (100 ml/l) at 7:50 → cultivation for 24 hours, 30 °C, 150 rpm
 - pH of medium = 10,0

- **27.5.:** all Erlenmeyer flasks removed at 8:00
 - OD₆₀₀ (30 °C) = 1,26
 - Bacterial suspension transferred to large centrifuge cuvettes → centrifugation for 10 minutes, 10 000 g, 4 °C
 - Supernatant was removed → 50 ml of saline was added into each cuvette
 - 450 ml of suspension with OD₆₀₀ = 5,14
 - Sample preparation: pre-weighed amount of WCF/HM/gypsum transferred into to the prepared vials and thoroughly mixed → addition of suspension/saline/HCl → mixture stirred with a sterile spatula/spoon and pores mechanically squeezed out → vibration of 30-120 seconds (depending on visual need to remove pores)
 - WCF: 10 ml of suspension/saline, 2 ml 2M HCl, 4 ml of saline
 - HM1, HM2: 10 ml of suspension/saline
 - Cultivation of samples and negative controls at 30 °C
 - Samples 41 (1-4), 42 (1-4) – addition of MICP solution (5 ml) each 48-72 hours
 - Samples 41 (5-8), 42 (5-8) – addition of saline (5 ml) each 48-72 hours (controls)
 - Samples 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40 – **WITHOUT ADDITION OF MICP/SALINE**

EXPERIMENT No. 15 (resp. GACR 14) – bricks

- **11.11.:** inoculation of Erlenmeyer flasks (4x400 ml) with LB + sodium sesquicarbonate (100 ml/l) at 7:45 → cultivation for 24 hours, 30 °C, 150 rpm
- **12.11.:** all Erlenmeyer flasks removed at 7:45
 - Bacterial suspension transferred to large centrifuge cuvettes → centrifugation for 10 minutes, 10 000 g, 4 °C
 - Supernatant was removed → 70 ml of saline was added into each cuvette = 280 ml, the pellet was resuspended and mixed into 2 cuvettes
 - Centrifugation again for 10 minutes, 10 000 g, 4 °C → supernatant was removed → 100 ml of MICP was added into both cuvettes
 - 400 ml of suspension with $OD_{600} = 5,71$
 - Sample preparation: pre-weighed amount of WCF (240 g WCF + 24 g gypsum) and HM1 (240 g HM1 + 24 g gypsum) were transferred into to the prepared boxes and thoroughly mixed → addition of suspension/saline/HCl → mixture stirred with a sterile spatula/spoon and pores mechanically squeezed out → vibration of 30-120 seconds (depending on visual need to remove pores)
 - WCF: 100 ml of suspension + 60 ml saline + 20 ml 2M HCl
 - HM1: 100 ml
 - Cultivation of samples at 30 °C **WITHOUT ADDITION OF MICP/SALINE**

- Cultivation/drying of samples at 30 °C from 12 November to 21 November

- From 21 November to 1 December: drying in the laboratory at room temperature (20–22 °C)
- 1 December: samples at CTU Prague

HM1+gypsum

WCF+gypsum

